

5-FLUOROURACIL CONTROLLED RELEASE FROM POLY (VINYLCAPROLACTAM-CO-METHACRYLIC ACID) COPOLYMERIC MICROSPHERES

Peddagani Rama Krishna*

Dept of Chemistry, P.S.Govt Degree College, Penukonda, Anantapuram, A.P.India-515110.

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*Correspondence for

Author

Peddagani Rama
Krishna

Dept of Chemistry,
P.S.Govt Degree College,
Penukonda, Anantapuram,
A.P.India-515110

ABSTRACT

In the study pH sensitive poly Vinylcaprolactam methacrylic acid (VCL-co-MAA) microspheres were cross linked with N,N-methylene bis acrylamide (NNMBA) prepared by free radical emulsion polymerization. This was done by using vinylcaprolactam, methacrylic acid, and NNMBA with varying amounts. 5-Fluorouracil (5-FU) is an anticancer drug which was mixed into these microspheres during *in situ* polymerization. These microspheres were characterized by using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) techniques. XRD and DSC results indicated that there was uniform distribution of 5-FU drug particles in microspheres, and SEM pictures suggest that the microspheres are in spherical shape. Both encapsulation efficiency and

release patterns are found to be dependent on the amount of cross linking agent and amount of drug loaded. The release 5-Fluorouracil was studied in phosphate buffer solutions of different pH 2, 5, and 7.2 Furthermore, *in vitro* release studies indicated the release of 5-FU up to 10 hours.

KEYWORDS: 5-Fluorouracil, microspheres, methacrylic acid, Vinylcaprolactam.

INTRODUCTION

A well designed controlled drug delivery system can overcome some of the problems of conventional therapy and enhance the therapeutic efficacy of a given drug. Even though controlled release (CR) technology is a well-established science for releasing short-acting drugs, research efforts in this area are accelerating rapidly in view of the availability of

innumerable polymers to encapsulate drugs of interest.^[1-8] The release of active agents from biodegradable polymers has many advantages over synthetic polymers because they can be easily degraded in the body and provide the desired therapeutic effect. Such CR systems have many advantages over the conventional dosage forms, including improved efficacy/patient compliance, reduced toxicity and convenience.^[9-13] Among the various types of polymers employed in pharmaceutical applications, hydrophilic bio-polymers, such as sodium alginate, chitosan, etc.^[14-18] have been widely used, since these have many advantages over synthetic polymers. In earlier literature,^[19-23] a large number of stimuli-responsive polymers have been studied, whose release profiles depend on their physical states under the influence of external environmental factors such as temperature, pH, ionic strength, etc.

5-Fluorouracil is an anti metabolic drug, used extensively in cancer chemotherapy,^[24-28] and is an antimetabolite, which is used to prevent the subsequent scarring following trabeculectomy and to improve the prognosis for longterm retinal reattachment. 5-Fluorouracil in an acidic, water soluble,^[29] hydrophilic drug and is an antineoplastic agent of extensive use in clinical chemotherapy for the treatment of solid tumors. Intravenous administration of 5-Fluorouracil (5-FU) for colon cancer therapy produces severe systematic side effects due to its cytotoxic effect on normal cells. It acts principally as a thymidylate synthase inhibitor, interferes with nucleic acid synthesis, inhibits DNA synthesis, and eventually halts cell growth.^[30]

Poly (N-vinylcaprolactam) (PVCL) is a well-known biopolymer that exhibits lower critical solution temperature (LCST) and is sensitive to changes in polymer concentration, molecular weight and composition of solution^[31]. Synthesis of copolymers or block copolymers of PVCL as well as the swelling behaviour of N-vinylcaprolactam (VCL) and MAA copolymer have been investigated as a function of pH and surfactant concentration.^[32-34] In search of new material, we propose here, the development of VCL and MAA copolymer i.e. poly (VCL-co-MAA), which is a pH-sensitive microspheres for 5-fluorouracil drug delivery. In continuation of this research, we now propose to develop a copolymer of VCL-co-MAA by *in situ* free radical polymerization in the presence of 5-fluorouracil. The systems of this study were characterized by Fourier transform infrared (FTIR), spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimeter (DSC,) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). *In vitro* release of 5-fluorouracil was performed in pH 2, 5 and 7.2 solutions at 37⁰C and concluded that the release time was up to 12 hrs.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Vinylcaprolactam (VCL) was purchased from Aldrich (Milwaukee, WI, USA). Methacrylic acid (MAA), N,N-methylene bis acrylamide (NNMBA), Sodium lauryl sulfate, potassium per sulfate and calcium chloride were all purchased from s.d. fine chemicals (Mumbai, India). 5FU was purchased from MP Biochemical's (Eschwege, Germany).

Synthesis of Poly (N-vinyl caprolactam-co-Meth acrylic acid) Microspheres

Sodium lauryl sulfate (1 g) was dissolved in 80 ml water taken in a three-necked round bottom flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer, a condenser and a gas inlet to maintain the inert nitrogen atmosphere. The flask was immersed in an oil bath with a thermostatic control to maintain the desired temperature accurate to $\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. The solution was stirred at 800 rpm speed until it became clear and then 100 mg potassium per sulfate initiator was added. The required amounts of MAA, VCL, cross-linking agent, NNMBA and 5-FU were dissolved separately in 20 ml water. This mixture was added to the reaction mixture drop-wise using a dropping funnel and the reaction was continued for 8 h at 70°C to obtain optimum yields of the final product. The reaction mixture was taken out after 8 h and drop-wise added to 1% calcium chloride solution ^[35]. Particles were then isolated by centrifuging the product at a rotor speed of 12,000 rpm, washed with water and dried under vacuum at 40°C for 24 h. Seven different batches of formulations were prepared by varying the amounts of monomer, drug and the cross-linking agent. The compositions of all the formulations, viz., MAA-1 to MAA-7, prepared in this work are given in Table 1.

CHARACTERIZATION OF COPOLYMERS

FTIR spectroscopy

FTIR spectral data were obtained between 400 and 4000 cm^{-1} using IR spectrophotometer (GX, Perkin Elmer, MA) to confirm the formation of copolymer. The samples were prepared by finely grinding the microparticles with KBr and by exposing to the infrared radiation.

Thermal analysis

DSC (Rheometric Scientific, Surrey, UK) was performed by heating the samples from ambient to 400°C at the heating rate of $10^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ in a nitrogen atmosphere at the flow rate of 10 mL/min.

Scanning electron microscopy

For SEM measurements, 5-Fluorouracil-loaded particles were mounted on metal stubs using double-sided adhesive tape, dried in a vacuum chamber, sputter-coated with a gold layer of 10 nm thick and viewed under high resolution SEM (Mag.4000, Using FEI-QUANTA-200, IISC, Bangalore) to characterize the shape and morphology as well as to confirm the particle size.

Extent of swelling

In order to investigate the pH sensitivity of the carrier system, gravimetric experiments (swelling) were performed by measuring the weight gain versus time in pH 2, 5 and 7.2 (phosphate buffer) media at 37°C. Extent of swelling was measured by taking placebo microspheres in separate test bottles containing 2, 5 and 7.2 pH solutions. At fixed intervals of time, microspheres were removed from the media, blotted gently to remove the surface-adhered water droplets and weighed on an electronic microbalance accurate to ±0.0001 g. After weighing, samples were placed back into the test bottles. This step was repeated until the samples reached equilibrium.

$$\% \text{ Water uptake} = \left(\frac{\text{Wt of swollen Microspheres}(w_1) - \text{Wt of dry Microspheres}(w_2)}{\text{Wt of dry Microspheres}(w_2)} \right) \dots (1)$$

Determination of Amount of Drug Entrapped

The % 5-Fluorouracil loading and % encapsulation efficiency (EE) of 5-Fluorouracil loaded formulations were calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Drug loading} = \left(\frac{\text{Amount of drug in Microspheres}}{\text{Amount of Microspheres}} \right) \times 100 \dots (2)$$

$$\% \text{ Encapsulation efficiency} = \left(\frac{\text{Actual loading}}{\text{Theoretical loading}} \right) \times 100 \dots (3)$$

In vitro release

The *in vitro* release experiments were performed by taking 100 mg of 5-Fluorouracil loaded poly (VCL-co-MAA) microspheres in a flask containing 50 mL of buffer solution. Particles were placed in a buffer solution to study the release of 5-fluorouracil and dissolution was carried out in a tablet dissolution tester (Lab India, Mumbai, India) maintained at 37°C under constant stirring speed of 100 rpm. Aliquots (2 mL) were withdrawn at interval of 1 h and the dissolution media was replenished with fresh buffer solution to maintain the total volume

after each withdrawal. Samples were analyzed by UV Spectrophotometer (Lab India, Mumbai, India) at the fixed λ_{\max} value of 270 nm. The in vitro release experiments were performed in solution of pH 2, 5 and 7.2; the entire experiment lasted for 12 h.

Fig.1. Synthesis of Crosslinked Copolymer VCL-MAA

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

FTIR spectroscopy

Polymerization reaction leading to the formation of copolymer is given in Fig. 2. FTIR spectrum of MAA has been reported in the following literature.^[36] The characteristic peaks observed at 2616 and 1696 cm^{-1} are assigned to carboxylic acid groups and carbonyl stretching vibrations, respectively. However, additional characteristic peaks of MAA appear at 1449 and 1301 cm^{-1} due to the COC multiple bond stretching and COH bending vibrations, respectively. VCL Fig.2 showed characteristic bands at 3571 cm^{-1} for O–H stretching vibrations, while those bands observed at 2928 and 2857 cm^{-1} are due to C–H stretching vibrations. Carbonyl (C–O) stretching vibrations are seen at 1665 cm^{-1} , but the bands at 1390 and 1347 cm^{-1} are due to C–H stretching and C–H bending vibrations, respectively. The bands at 1259 and 1185 cm^{-1} belong to C–N stretching vibrations. In the case of the copolymer Fig.3, the region 1500–1700 cm^{-1} corresponds to the absorption bands of VCL and the copolymer. Amide band splits into a doublet at 1621 and 1615 cm^{-1} , while the formation of carbonyl stretching band in the copolymer indicates hydrogen bonding interactions between VCL and MAA in the copolymer.

The C=O peak is observed at 1714 cm^{-1} and the amide low-frequency splitting is likely to be caused by the formation of new hydrogen bonds between carboxyl O–H groups and amide groups. The high-frequency shift of C=O occurs due to the destruction of H-bonds between MAA carboxyl groups, which suggests the involvement of carboxyl groups in H-bonding. In the spectrum of VCL/MAA, the OH band appearing at 3398 cm^{-1} is shifted to lower

frequencies, implying the change in the nature of H-bonding, which further confirms the formation of H-bonds between amide and carboxyl groups. This FTIR spectrum confirms the synthesis of co polymeric microspheres of poly (VCL-co-MAA).

Fig.2. FTIR spectra of N-Vinylcaprolactam.

Fig.3. FTIR spectra of N-Vinylcaprolactam-co-methacrylic acid.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) studies

DSC tracings of (a) plain 5-FU, (b) plain Poly (VCL-co-MAA) microspheres, and (c) Poly (VCL-co-MAA) microspheres are depicted in Fig.4. The one set-melting peak of 5-FU is observed at 285.16°C. However, no characteristic peak of 5-FU is observed in the DSC curves of the drug-loaded microspheres, suggesting that drug is molecularly dispersed in the polymer matrix.

Fig.4. DSC thermo grams of (a) 5-FU, (b) plain (VCL-co-MAA) microspheres, and (c) 5-FU-loaded Poly (VCL-co-MAA) microspheres

X-ray diffraction studies

X-ray diffractograms of (a) placebo microspheres, (b) drugloaded microspheres, and (c) pure 5-FU drug are shown in Fig.5. These studies are useful to investigate the crystallinity of the drug in crosslinked microspheres. 5-FU has shown the characteristic intense peaks at 2θ of 25° due to its crystalline nature. However, these peaks disappeared in the 5-FU loaded microspheres, but only peaks observed in placebo polymer matrix were seen. XRD peak depends on the crystal size, but in the present study, for all the drug loadings, the characteristic peaks of 5-FU overlapped with noise of the coated polymer itself. Furthermore, loaded drug is amorphous, which is difficult to measure at the direction limit of the crystal size in the present case. This further confirms that drug is molecularly dispersed at a molecular level in the polymer matrix and hence, no crystals were found in the drugloaded matrices.

Fig.5. XRD spectra of (a) pure 5-FU, (b) Plain Poly (VCL-co-MAA) microspheres, and (c) 5-FU-loaded Poly (VCL-co-MAA) microspheres.

Scanning electron microscopy analysis

SEM photographs of single poly (VCL-co-MAA) microspheres were taken at 700X magnification which is shown in Fig.6. From Fig. 6, poly (VCL-co-MAA) microspheres

show almost spherical and rough surface. Size of the microspheres is found to be around 20 μm .

Fig.6. SEM micrographs of Poly (Vinylcaprolactam-co- methacrylic acid)

Encapsulation efficiency

Results of encapsulation efficiency for different formulations as a function of extents of drug lodging, crosslinking and monomer ratio are including in Table 1. % encapsulation efficiency increased systematically with increase in drug loading from 10 to 30% in the matrix, and their encapsulation efficiencies were 65, 68 and 72%, respectively. This increase in encapsulation efficiency is due to the availability of more free void space, through which lesser number of drug molecules will Transport. It is noticed that % encapsulation efficiency increased with increase in VCL content in the Poly (VCL-co-MAA) microspheres. For example, for the microspheres containing 20, 30, and 40 wt% VCL and 20 wt% of 5-FU, encapsulation efficiencies were 58, 61, and 68, respectively. For microspheres crosslinked with 10, 20, and 30 wt% NNMBA, encapsulation efficiencies (68, 67, and 62) decreased with increase in crosslinker content in the microspheres respectively. Such a decreasing trend is due to increase in crosslinking density, because the microspheres become rigid, thereby reducing the free volume space within the polymer matrix and hence, a reduction in encapsulation efficiency.

Table 1: Formulation codes, percent encapsulation of drug-loaded microspheres

Formulation	VCL (%)	MAA (%)	NNMBA (%)	5-FU (%)	Encapsulation efficiency \pm SD (%)
MAA-1	40	60	2	10	65 \pm 0.7
MAA-2	40	60	2	20	67 \pm 0.4
MAA-3	40	60	2	30	72 \pm 0.9
MAA-4	40	60	1	20	68 \pm 0.9
MAA-5	40	60	3	20	62 \pm 0.3
MAA-6	30	70	2	20	61 \pm 0.6
MAA-7	20	80	2	20	58 \pm 0.5

Standard deviations have been calculated at 95% confidence limit by the least-squares method.

Drug release kinetics

Drug release kinetics is analyzed by plotting the cumulative release data vs time and by fitting these data to the exponential equations of the type.^[37]

$$(M_t/M_\infty) = kt^n \text{ --- (4)}$$

Here, M_t/M_∞ represents the fractional drug release at time t ; k is a constant characteristic of the drug-polymer system and ' n ' is an empirical parameter characterizing the release mechanism. Using the least square procedure, the estimated values of ' n ' and k for all the formulation are given in Table 2. If $n = 0.5$, then drug diffuses and releases from the polymer matrix following a Fickian diffusion. For $n > 0.5$, an anomalous or non-fickian type drug diffusion occurs. If $n = 1$, a completely nonFickian of case II release kinetics is operative. The intermediary values ranging between 0.5 and 1 are attributed to the anomalous type of transport. The values of k increased with increasing % of loading of 5-FU in the microspheres, but ' n ' values decreased with decrease in % of loading of 5-FU. This indicates that the interaction between the microspheres and drug are in similar lines studied from the release kinetics Eqn (4) proposed by Ritger and Peppas. The values of exponent ' n ' ranges between 0.5674 and 1.1363 as calculated from empirical, which indicated that drug release followed by an anomalous nontransport occurs. The correlation coefficient values are in the range of 0.910 to 0.958, suggesting a good fit experimental release data.

Table 2: Release Kinetics Parameters of Different Formulations

Formulation code	k	n	Correlation coefficient, r
MAA-1	0.1359	0.6953	0.910
MAA-2	0.2346	0.8653	0.921
MAA-3	0.3113	1.1363	0.913
MAA-4	0.1547	0.5674	0.921
MAA-5	0.1861	0.6802	0.932
MAA-6	0.8312	0.8316	0.958
MAA-7	0.2174	0.7474	0.915

IN VITRO RELEASE STUDIES

Effect of 5-Fluorouracil

5-FU is a water-soluble drug and therefore, it is difficult to encapsulate it into hydrophobic polymers by solvent exchange process. In the present case, release profiles ranging from 62 to 81% could be achieved for different copolymer compositions. The % of encapsulation efficiency data are presented in Table 1. Fig.7 displays the drug release characteristics of the formulations containing different amounts of drug. The above results indicate that 5-FU release is up to 10 hours. From these groups, it is noticed that the faster release rates have

been observed for the formulations containing higher amount of 5-FU than those microspheres containing lower amounts of 5-FU in the matrix. Release data with regard to drug content is in the order of 30>20> 10% of 5-FU. A prolonged drug release was observed for formulation containing lower amount of 5-FU. It is understood that the release rate becomes quite slower when a lower amount of drug is present in the matrix, probably due to the availability of more free-void spaces, through which lesser number of drug molecules could possibly transport. Generally, drug release through microspheres depends upon the particle size, polymer crystallinity, surface character, molecular weight, polymer composition, etc. Hence in the present study, the above said parameters may be responsible for the release trend with respect to drug content in the microspheres.

Fig.7. % of cumulative release of drug through Poly (VCL-co-MAA) microspheres crosslinked with 2 wt% NNMBA and containing 10 (Δ), 20 (■), 30% (◆) of 5-Fluorouracil

Effect of cross linking

The % of cumulative release data vs time plots for varying amounts of crosslinker, NNMBA, i.e., 10, 20, and 30 w% at a fixed amount of drug (20%) are depicted in Fig.8. The % of cumulative release is quite fast and large at lower amount of NNMBA, whereas the release is quite slower at higher amount i.e., at 30% NNMBA. This is because at higher concentration of NNMBA, the polymeric chains will become rigid due to higher contraction of microvoids, thereby giving a decrease in % of cumulative release of the drug.

Fig.8. % of cumulative release of the drug through Poly (VCL-co-MAA) microspheres crosslinked with 20 wt% of 5-Flourouracil and containing 1 (♦), 2 (■), and 3% (Δ) of NNMBA

Effect of vinyl caprolactam

Effect of VCL content on encapsulation efficiency and *in vitro* release of 5-FU was investigated and the data are given in Table 1. *In vitro* release profiles of 5-FU for formulations prepared by taking different amounts of VCL with 20% of 5-FU and 2% NNMBA are shown in Fig.9. Higher release rates were observed for the formulations prepared with higher amounts of VCL (i.e., 40%) than those formulations prepared using lower amounts of VCL. Slower drug release is observed from formulations prepared with lower amount of VCL, which is due to the hydrophilic nature of both the drug and VCL in the copolymer.^[38]

Fig.9. % of cumulative release of 5-FU drug through Poly (VCL-co-MAA) microspheres crosslinked with 2 wt% NNMBA and 20% 5-FU for different ratios of vinyl caprolactam, i.e., 20 (Δ), 30 (■), and 40% (♦)

Effect of pH

The *in vitro* release of 5-Fluorouracil loaded microspheres displayed in Fig.10 suggest a pH-responsive property of the copolymer in which inter-polymer complex are formed in acidic

media and dissociated in the alkaline pH environment.^[39, 40] It was observed that 5-Fluorouracil was significantly retarded in acidic pH media, while it was rapidly released in alkaline pH. The 5-Fluorouracil release rates from the Poly(vinylcaprolactam –co-methacrylic acid) microspheres have been measured at pH 2, 5 and 7.2, See Fig.10 .The 5-Fluorouracil release rate at pH 7.2, is higher release rate may be related to the higher swelling ratio of the microspheres and the weak H-bonding interaction between drug and polymer network, the carboxylic groups of methacrylic acid present along the macromolecular chains in the drugloaded device are almost completely ionized, thus causing the polymeric chains to undergo extensive relaxation due to electrostatic repulsion among the charged carboxylic groups. This the finally results in the higher swelling ratio.

While in pH 2 and 5, the amount of 5-Fluorouracil released is decrease may be related to the lower swelling ratio of the microspheres, and unionized carboxylic groups do not induce the chain relaxation process. The drug molecules were protonated and unable to form strong hydrogen bonds like at pH 7.2 with the microspheres matrix. Additionally, carboxylic groups in the matrix were fully protonated to give –COOH, which could form hydrogen bonds with the structure of microspheres.^[41]

Fig. 10. Effect of pH on The Release of 5-Fluorouracil at 37⁰C, pH 2(Δ), 5(■) and7.2 (◆).

CONCLUSION

A new class of microspheres has been synthesized by free radical copolymerization of VCL with MAA in the presence of crosslinking agents NNMBA. These pH sensitive microspheres respond to small change of pH to much sharper extant than other pH-sensitive microspheres, which may be due to the presence carboxylic groups of MAA in the microspheres. 5-Fluorouracil was loaded as model drug. The effect of monomeric composition, degree of VCL and natural monomer on drug release were investigated. Microspheres with higher

amount of VCL showed more drug release than those microspheres with other contents of VCL. The 5-Fluorouracil release rate at pH 7.2, is higher release than pH 2 and 5. This is due to the higher swelling ratio of the microspheres, and the weak H-bonding interaction between drug and polymer network. The *in vitro* drug release indicated that release kinetics depend upon copolymer composition, amount of crosslinking agent used and amount of 5-Fluorouracil present in the microspheres.

REFERENCES

1. Hickey T, Kreutzer D, Burgess, DJ, Moussy F. *Biomaterials*. 2002; 23: 1649-1656.
2. Burgess DJ, Hickey AJ. in: Swarbrick J, Boylan JC. (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Pharmaceutical Technology*, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1994; pp. 1-29.
3. Thombre AG, Cardinal JR, in: Swarbrick J, Boylan JC. (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Pharmaceutical Technology*, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1990; pp. 61-88.
4. Sinha VR, Trehan A. *J Control Release*. 2003; 90: 261-280.
5. Anderson JM, Shive MS. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev* 1997; 28: 5-24.
6. Wu NL, Ding J. *Biomaterials* 2004; 25: 5821-5830.
7. Middleton JC, Tipton AJ. *Biomaterials* 2000; 21: 2335-2346.
8. Murthy RSR. in: Jain NK (Eds.), *Controlled and Novel Drug Delivery*, CBS Publisher, New Delhi, 1997; pp. 27-51.
9. Jain NK. *Controlled and Novel drug delivery*, 04 Edition, 236-237, 21.
10. Soppimath KS, Aminabhavi T M, Rudzinski WE. *J. Control. Rel.* 2001; 70: 1-20.
11. Soppimath KS, Kulkarni AR, Aminabhavi TM. *J. Control. Rel.* 2001; 75: 331-345.
12. Soppimath KS Kulkarni AR, Aminabhavi TM. *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* 2002; 53: 87-98.
13. Uhrich UE, Cannizzaro SM, Langer RS, Shakesheff KM. *Chem. Rev.* 1999; 99: 3181-98.
14. Laukkanen A, Hietala S, Maunu SL, Tenhu H. *Macromolecules*. 2000; 33: 8703-8708.
15. Friedman M J. *Agric. Food Chem.* 2003; 51: 4504-26.
16. Mundargi RC, Patil SA, Aminabhavi TM. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 2007; 69: 130-141.
17. Shi J, Alves NM, Mano JF. *Macromol. Biosci.* 2006; 6: 358-63.
18. Babu VR, Hosamani KM, Aminabhavi TM. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 2008; 71: 208-217.
19. Kanazawa H, Yamamoto K, Matsushima Y, Takai N, Kikuchi A, Sakurai Y, Okano T. *Anal. Chem.* 1996; 68: 100-5.
20. Vihola H, Laukkanen A, Hirvonen J, Tenhu H. *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* 2002; 16: 69-74.
21. Lugo MT, Peppas NA. *Macromolecules*. 1999; 32: 6646-6651.
22. Coughlan DC, Quilty FP, Corrigan O. I. *J. Control. Rel.* 2004; 98: 97-114.

23. Mundargi RC, Agnihotri SA, Patil SA, Kulkarni PV, Mallikarjuna NN, Aminabhavi TM. *J. Microencapsul.* 2008; 25: 228-40.
24. Heidelberger C, *Cancer Medicine*, 2nd ed. Lea and Febiger, Philadelphia, 1982; p.801.
25. Waxman S, Scanlon KJ, Greenspan EM. *Clinical Interpretation and Practice in Chemotherapy*, Raven Press, New York, 1982; p.39.
26. Sommadossi JP, Gewirtz DA, Diasio RB, Aubert C, Cano JP, Goldman ID. Rapid catabolism of 5-fluorouracil in freshly isolated rat hepatocytes as analyzed by high performance liquid chromatography, *J. Biol. Chem.* 1982; 257: 8171.
27. Einmahl S, Zignani M, Varesio E, Heller J, Veuthey JL, Tabatabay C, Gurny R. Concomitant and controlled release of dexamethasone and 5-fluorouracil from poly (orthoester), *Int.J.Pharm.* 1999; 185: 189-198.
28. Fournier E, Passirani C, Colin N, Bretona P, Sagodiraa S, Benoit JP. Development of novel 5-FU-loaded poly (methylidene malonate 2.1.2)-based microspheres for the treatment of brain cancers, *Eur.J.Pharm.Biopharm.* 2004; 57: 189-97.
29. Ermis D, Yuksel A, Preparation of spray-dried microspheres of indomethacin and examination of the effects of coating on dissolution rates, *J.Microencapsul.* 1999; 16: 315-24.
30. Parker WB, Cheng YC. Metabolism and mechanism of action of 5-fluorouracil, *Pharmacol. Ther.* 1990; 48: 381-95.
31. Lau ACW, Wu C. Thermally sensitive and biocompatible poly (N-vinyl caprolactam) Synthesis and characterization of high molar mass linear chains. *Macromolecules.* 1999; 32: 581-584.
32. Shtanko NI, Lequieu W, Goethals EJ, Du Prez FE. pH- and thermo-responsive properties of poly(N-vinylcaprolactam-co-acrylic acid) copolymers. *Polym Int*, 2003; 52: 1605–10.
33. Makhaeva EE, Tenhu H, Khokhlov AR. 2002. Behavior of poly(N-vinylcaprolactam-co-methacrylic acid) macromolecules in aqueous solution: Interplay between Coulombic and hydrophobic interaction. *Macromolecules*, 1996; 35: 1870–6.
34. Mundargi RC, Rangaswamy V, Aminabhavi TM. pH-Sensitive oral insulin delivery systems using Eudragit microspheres. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm*, 2011; 28: 384-94.
35. Babu VR, Sairam M, Hosamani KM, Aminabhavi TM. Development of 5-Fluorouracil Loaded Poly (Acrylamide-co-methylmethacrylate) Novel Core-Shell Microspheres: In Vitro Release Studies,” *International Journal of Pharmaceutics.* 2006, 325: 55-62.

36. Mundargi RC, Agnihotri SA, Patil SA, Aminabhavi TM. Graft copolymerization of methacrylic acid onto guar gum using potassium persulfate as an initiator. *J Appl Polym Sci*, 2006; 101: 618–23.
37. Ritger PL, Peppas NAA; simple equation for description of solute release, I; Fickian and non-Fickian release from non-swellable devices in the form of slabs, spheres, cylinders or discs. *J. Control. Rel.* 1987; 5: 37-42.
38. Prabaharn M, Grailer JJ, Steeber DA, Gong S. Stimuli responsive chitosan-graft-poly (N-vinyl caprolactam) as promising material for controlled hydrophobic drug delivery. *Macromol Biosci* 2008; 8: 843-51.
39. Kumar A, Lahiri SS, Punyani S, Singh H. Synthesis and characterization of pH sensitive poly(PEGDMA-MAA) copolymeric microparticles for oral insulin delivery. *J Appl Polym Sci*, 2008; 107: 863–71.
40. Kumar A, Lahiri SS, Singh H. Development of PEGDMA: MAA based hydrogel microparticles for oral insulin delivery. *Int J Pharm*, 2006; 323: 117–24.
41. Chen Y, Liang Y. 2TA Sustained Release of Model Drug from a Novel Poly acrylic acid – poly aluminium Chloride Super. *Iranian polymer journal* 2T. 2010; 19: 531-540.